

IMPORTANCE OF METONYMY IN ENGLISH AND USE IN OTHER LANGUAGES DURING THE TRANSLATION PROCESS

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Abstract: This article explains what metonymy is and its importance. In addition, important aspects used in the process of translation in other languages are highlighted.

Key words: metonymy, linguist, linguistic phenomena, phrase, theory.

In the period of development of information and communication technologies of the 21st century, the introduction of a new word, phrase or term one language to the second language has become a natural state. In addition to the enrichment and development of the language that is the ability to replace each foreign word with a corresponding lexical unit in its lexical base. Therefore, languages are enriched, polished and beautified by borrowing words from each other. It is no exaggeration to say that word transfer from language to language has become an undeniable linguistic fact of our time. Translation metonymy in translation has always been one of the issues of translation studies that require research.

Metonymy is considered to be a phenomenon of transfer of meaning which is attracting the attention of both linguists and translators. Linguists try to reveal the characteristic features of semes and sememes in polysemous words to this transfer of meaning. Literary scholars consider various means of image in polysemic words to be the factors that create them. In both directions, the goal is the same, and that is to study the multiple meanings of words and their stylistic meanings, learning multiple meanings of the word plays an important role, first of all, for the lexical essence¹⁴. Because one word has different meanings, it requires correct use in oral and written speech. The shades of meaning of words are also widely studied as an important visual tool in fiction.

In our country, we are creating favorable opportunities for introducing advanced methods of teaching using modern pedagogical and information and communication technologies, improving the system of training specialists with proficiency in foreign

¹⁴Islamova, M. Sh. "Fundamentals of Forming a Professional Worldview." Science and Education. Special issue1 2021. p78-87

languages, and developing international cooperation. Also in the process of learning a language, comparing it with one's native language helps to better understand the grammatical aspect of the newly learned foreign language.

J. Buranov is one of the linguists who had carried out a number of theoretical and practical works on the comparative study of the Uzbek and English languages. According to him, comparative typology is a part of general linguistic typology "which studied two or more specific language systems, certain categories in languages deductively separately. By comparing linguistic phenomena in language systems, they create common typological rules and laws. In a two way comparison of two language systems, the descriptive material of each compared language system is compared separately."¹⁵

Metonymy comes from the Greek word "metonymia" which translates to "change of name"¹⁶. Metonymy is a figure of speech in which an object or idea is referred to by the name of something closely associated with it, as opposed to by its own name. Metonymy involves a word or phrase substituting or standing in for another word or phrase.

Though many people might use metonymy subconsciously in their every day speech, writers use it in fiction, essays, and poetry for a number of reasons¹⁷.

1. Metonymy allows writers to express themselves creatively.

Substituting a different word or phrase, as long as connection still makes sense, gives writers the freedom to get more creative with language.

2. Metonymy gives writers the ability to make single words or phrases more powerful.

You can add meaning and complexity to even the most ordinary word by having it stand in to mean something else. For example, take the phrase "the pen is mightier than sword" which contains two examples of metonymy. "Pen" and "sword" are every day words, but when substituted for "written words" and "military force", their meaning become much more symbolic. The phrase implies that the written word is more powerful than military force.

3. Metonymy helps writers be more concise.

¹⁵ Buranov, J. Comparative typology of English and Turkic languages. Moscow. Higher School. 1983

¹⁶ www.google.uz

¹⁷ Goossens, L. "The interaction of Metaphor and Metonymy in Expressions for Linguistic Action" in Cognitive Linguistics 1990. p323-340

Short phrases can sometimes be punchier and more profound. Journalists and speech writers often use metonymy to replace complicated ideas with shorter, simpler alternatives to help audiences better understand complicated concepts¹⁸.

People use figurative language every day whether they realize it or not. Common examples of metonymy in language include:

Hollywood has been releasing a surprising amount of sci-fi movies lately.

Hollywood is a literally a district in Los Angeles, but because it has come to be linked to the entertainment business, celebrities, and movi-making, it is a common example of metonymy.

The kitchen is coming along nicely.

This example means that the renovation work on the kitchen is moving quickly and efficiently. Because kitchen is the room being worked on, we can simplify the sentence using only “the kitchen” as a metonymy phrase.

Here are some another short examples:

“Plate” can mean an entire plate of food.

“Lend me your ears” is a popular metonymy phrase.

“Jeff is a real silver fox!” This is a metonymy that means that Jeff is an attractive older man.

“Give me a hand” means to give someone help.

Because associative and referential thinking are so natural and automatic to us, metonymies can be found and understood frequently in everyday language, literature, and pop culture. Metonymies allow for brevity by replacing lists with an associated category. They summarize complicated processes or programs with shortened phrases. Finally, they emphasize the most important and defining characteristics of a subject such as a “Margherita” for a “Margherita pizza”¹⁹. Besides that metonymy and metaphor are similar, but they are not the same thing. First of all, metonymy associates the qualities of one word or phrase with another word or phrase. Secondly metaphor, however, substitutes a word or phrase with another word or phrase to draw a comparison to their similarities. In conclusion any language has its own vocabulary and forms. The importance of the word in the process of translation between different languages is very great. By properly comparing and translating it into languages, it can provide a lot of information for learners.

¹⁸ Goossens, L. “The interaction of Metaphor and Metonymy in Expressions for Linguistic Action” in Cognitive Linguistics 1990. p323-340

¹⁹ Barnden, J. “Metaphor and Metonymy: A Practical Deconstruction”. 2006. P49-54

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